

A MARKETING APPROACH TO CLARIFYING THE CONCEPT OF QUALITY OF EDUCATIONAL SERVICES

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Abstract. This article examines the reform of the education system, the classification of higher education and training areas and specializations in the country, the improvement of the educational infrastructure, the adoption of investment programs aimed at the development of the education sector, the introduction of advanced foreign innovations, and the marketing approach as educational services.

Keywords: education, system, specialty, infrastructure, development, innovation, society, industry.

МАРКЕТИНГОВЫЙ ПОДХОД К УТОЧНЕНИЮ ПОНЯТИЯ КАЧЕСТВА ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫХ УСЛУГ

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается реформирование системы образования, классификация направлений и специальностей высшего образования и подготовки в стране, совершенствование образовательной инфраструктуры, принятие инвестиционных программ, направленных на развитие сферы образования, внедрение передовых зарубежных инноваций, а маркетинговый подход как образовательные услуги.

Ключевые слова: образование, система, специальность, инфраструктура, развитие, инновации, общество, промышленность.

The innovative nature of the economy requires special attention to the qualitative aspect of social development. Education is an important element in the socio-economic construction of society, and it has its place in ensuring its future development and the quality of labor resources. Even in our country today, financial and natural resources are rapidly changing to intellectual resources based on the knowledge economy.

Today, the quality of education is becoming one of the issues that cannot be postponed. Therefore, it is required to apply a marketing approach to decision-making on this issue at the state level. Today, not only enterprises, but also at the state level, the attitude towards marketing activities has changed radically. Initially, the "4R" complex of marketing was developed, but today this complex is giving way to the "4I", which combines social and economic development in society. "4I" complex includes institutions, infrastructure, investment and innovation.

The implementation of this complex is carried out on the basis of the reform of the education system, classification of HEIs and educational areas and specialties in the country, improvement of the educational infrastructure, adoption of investment programs aimed at the development of the educational sector, introduction of advanced foreign innovations.

Table 1

A marketing approach to improving the quality of educational services

Traditional Approach (4R)	A modern approach (4I)
Product – type of educational service.	Institutions - education is a unique type of service, which is produced only by educational institutions.

Price – formation of an acceptable price for educational services. In this case, the price serves as a quality factor	Infrastructure - improvement of the educational infrastructure based on the needs of the times, based on the classification of higher educational institutions and educational areas, specialties,
Place - it is envisaged that educational institutions will be located in large cities as much as possible, or it will be implemented through academies, universities and special institutes	Investment - acceptance of investment programs aimed at the development of the educational sector, improvement of their material and technical base
Promotion – effective use of communication tools in promoting educational services	Innovation - improving the quality of educational services based on the introduction of advanced pedagogical and educational innovations

It is not necessary to link it to various economic crises in order to explain the fact that this complex has not been implemented until now in order to ensure the quality of education. This is primarily:

Introduction to the concept of "quality of education";

It is based on the analysis of factors affecting the quality of education.

Since the second half of the 20th century, the "Quality Revolution" has occurred throughout the world. The world's leading manufacturing enterprises began to focus on product quality rather than quantity and quality. Quality is emerging as a key driver of competitiveness.

Quality - as a general concept, it is a set of characteristics and private signs of products, materials, types of work, work, services, etc., based on meeting the needs and requirements of people, and is evaluated by their full compliance with the requirements and their tasks. Such compatibility is mainly determined by standards, contracts, agreements, and consumer requirements.

Attention to quality and the stages of its development can be logically divided into the following periods:

1. 60s of the 20th century - the main factor in market competitiveness is product quality.
2. The 70s of the 20th century - the stage of transition from product quality to production technology quality.
3. The 80s of the 20th century - the period of transition to the quality management system stage.
4. Since the 90s of the 20th century, the quality of education, the quality of intellectual resources, and the quality of human life began to appear as the main factor.

Quality of education- is considered a social category and determines the state and result of the educational process in the society, as well as the formation and development of the professional, domestic and civil competence of the individual, in accordance with the demands and needs of the society. The quality of education is evaluated through a set of indicators describing various aspects of the educational activity of the educational institution. These indicators include educational content, teaching forms and methods, material and technical base, staff structure, etc., which ensure the development of the competence of learners.

Quality of education- is a set of knowledge acquired in specific conditions, necessary for improving the quality of human life and achieving a specific goal.

Quality of education in higher education- is a multi-faceted, multi-level dynamic concept related to the contextual indicators of the educational model, institutional goals and objectives and specific standards of the educational system, educational institutions, curricula and subjects.

Quality of knowledge- it is determined by the fundamentality, quality and necessity of the knowledge obtained after completing the educational process. The term "quality of education" has different meanings depending on the following factors:

- interests of higher education participants;
- interrelation of concepts such as input data, educational processes, output data, goals and tasks;
- characteristics or description of the academic field being evaluated;
- the period of historical development of higher education.

Also, the term quality of education has the following different levels of definition:

- quality as the highest indicator;
- quality - in the form of fully achieved activity;
- quality in the form of improved and improved performance.

The definitions of "quality of education" presented above have their advantages and disadvantages depending on the historical period of educational reforms.

The quality of education can be considered both as an absolute and as a relative concept.

In the absolute concept of the quality of education, it is meant to reflect the status, position and superiority of the educational institution. Such an ideal concept creates conditions for the development and strengthening of the image of the educational institution and represents the pursuit of the highest level of educational standards in terms of the quality of education. The quality of education can also be considered as a relative concept. In this case, quality education is not considered the main attribute (integral part, main feature) of the service and is evaluated by the compliance of the educational process with the state educational standard. Therefore, the quality of education can be defined as a relative concept in two different ways:

Education is an important area of social life. It is education that forms the intellectual, cultural and spiritual state of society.

Educational content and its directions are reflected in educational standards and programs. When evaluating the quality of education, it is necessary to take into account the following elements:

- possessor, disseminator of knowledge;
- knowledge transmitters;
- knowledge transfer technology;
- learner;
- level of knowledge;
- the necessity and necessity of acquired knowledge;
- the need and opportunity to acquire new knowledge.

The quality of education is primarily determined by the quality, level and qualification of knowledge holders and distributors.

Scientific and technical progress creates new tools and weapons. For this reason, in order to introduce modern technologies and technical means into production, to organize the production of competitive products suitable for the world market, the graduate is required to continuously study new innovative technologies and techniques in his production work, that is, there is a need to acquire knowledge. As a result, in addition to imparting knowledge to the student, it is necessary to form and develop his ability to learn independently.

Based on the above, when determining the quality of education, quality indicators can be divided into the following groups;

- quality of teaching staff;
- material and technical base of the educational institution;
- the basis of the teaching staff;
- quality of training programs;
- quality of students;
- infrastructure quality;
- quality of knowledge;
- innovation activity of management;
- implementation of innovative processes;
- demand for graduates;
- competitiveness of graduates in the labor market;
- graduate achievements.

The main focus in the educational process is on the teacher. Therefore, the organization of the quality of education begins with the proper formation of the teaching staff.

Material and technical base of the higher educational institution It is determined by the cost and availability of the basic means (buildings and structures, machines and devices, laboratories, ARM fund, etc.) necessary for the organization of the educational process, scientific research works and developments.

The scientific potential of professors-teachers of a particular higher educational institution is taken into account when justifying the teaching staff. Academic capacity is determined as a percentage by the ratio of the number of teachers with degrees and titles to the total number of teachers in the main state.

Also, their average age can be taken into account when evaluating the teaching staff.

The quality of educational programs is assessed not only by their compliance with the requirements of the state educational standard, but also by the innovative nature of their content.

Quality of learners is the most basic and important indicator affecting the final result. Because at the center of the educational process are consumers of knowledge - learners.

It is for them that trainings are conducted, educational literature is written, and new educational technologies are developed. For this reason, it is necessary and necessary to pay attention to the quality of students when determining the quality of education. Because as a result of the educational process, these are the ones who should give the final quality intellectual product (staff).

Infrastructure quality, that is, the quality of the structural structure of the educational institution: the management structure (the number and composition of the rector, vice-rectors, heads of departments, faculties and departments) and the number of administrative and

management staff, professors and teaching assistants is sufficient for optimal and effective management of the educational process, and economic is based on its acceptability.

Quality of knowledge is determined by its fundamentality, strength and the degree to which it is needed in production. The innovative activity of the management and the implementation of innovative processes in the educational institution are directly evaluated by the quality indicators of management and management of the educational process in accordance with the requirements of the time.

We evaluate these listed factors as internal environmental factors in educational marketing. We can include the following in the external environmental factors of OTM:

In the future, social factors will lead to a reduction in the number of students, changes in the final state certification, entrance tests, and the reform of the higher education system. Depending on the demands of employers, the nature of training can also change radically.

Technological factors are considered important in the introduction of information technologies in the field and their effective use, and are reflected in the transition of the educational process to a distance form, the organization of independent education, and others.

Economic factors are more related to the standard of living of the population, the ability to pay, and are reflected in the motivation of students to study. Also, changes in the banking and financial and tax systems, changes in interest rates, financing of innovative projects also affect the demand for educational services.

Political factors include the state policy in the field of education, the direction of the state policy on the development of secondary and special vocational education, increasing interest in technical areas, further improving the system of training qualified personnel, ensuring the international integration of personnel, recognition of documents on foreign education.

In the factor analysis of the service market, we can recommend dividing the main influences into the following criteria that influence supply and demand in the market.

We can use the PEST-analysis matrix for this.

Table 2

PEST-analysis matrix of criteria affecting supply and demand for graduate personnel in the market of educational services

Political	Economical
<p style="text-align: center;"><i>Existing legislation regulating the educational services market</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - rule of law and future sustainability in education; - government policy in the field of educational services under international law. - the state's encouragement of competition in the education system - norms of state control of entities in the field of educational services - democratic changes in the country and in the management of the education system; - market pressure by groups; 	<p style="text-align: center;"><i>Changes and trends in the economy</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - economic situation (GDP) - dynamics of refinancing rates - inflation rate - investment environment in the network - trends in international education systems; - climate and seasonal effects - market conditions and service sales cycles - solvency of the population - changes in the solvency of major employers - the uniqueness of creating educational

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - expansion of the international educational services market; - environmental problems; - democratic principles of elections; - relations between local authorities and HEIs; - other effects of the state on the field of educational services; · the existence of legislation regulating entrepreneurship in various sectors of the economy; · financial support of the state; · legal guarantees of economic activity; - policy of starting new jobs due to reorganization of the composition of enterprises and institutions - programs to create new jobs in the service sector 	<p>services</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the scale of moving educational services in the market - dynamics of needs for educational services - dynamics of exchange rates in the educational services market - the composition of the main expenses (energy sources, transport, raw materials and equipment, communication) - the amount of expenses spent on the organization of educational service provision areas. - the state of state control of the service sector and sanctions
Society	Technology
<p>Demographics</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - changes in legislation regulating social factors - changes in labor relations legislation - the degree of proportionality of the structure of income and expenses - established values, culture and traditions in society. - policies aimed at increasing the level of employment - trend of changes in standard of living - healthy lifestyle - attitude to work and rest - attitude to education - brand, reputation, and technological image of the higher education institution - customer behavior model - the level of imitation of fashion and models - the impact of important events and factors - customer opinion and attitude - consumer preference and level of utility of services 	<p>Development of competitive technologies</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the size of the marketing budget, the level of research funding - related and unrelated technologies to educational services - complementary technologies and solutions - technology life cycle - the variability and adaptability of new technologies - size and level of educational services - the level of provision of information and communication tools, the influence of the Internet - the level of consumer acceptance of the technology - technology legislation - innovative potential - licensing and patenting of technologies - intellectual property issues - structural changes and modernization of education; - increase in technical provision of education and introduction of new

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - relations with oav (mass media). - the level of communication with the client, ethics and culture - ethnic / religious factors - advertising and public relations (pr) - degree of exposure to advertising - provision of qualified personnel - population employment dynamics - a positive approach to increasing the share of services in a certain sector of the economy; - differentiation of income in society. 	<p>technologies;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - changes in educational service provision conditions and salary levels; - dynamics of investments; - service intensity - high level of competitiveness (characteristics and quality of service providers and goods and services produced (rendered) by them, use of know-how and information)
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. The development strategy of educational institutions in improving and managing the quality of higher education services should include the following three parts: 1) compliance with the minimum requirements of state accreditation standards; 2) compliance with the changing requirements of potential employers and society, and 3) indicators of the performance of scientific and research work developed by the educational institution for self-improvement

Marketing services department in all educational institutions should work intensively today. The marketing services department of educational institutions should be coordinated with each other based on the characteristics of the educational institution.

A method of analyzing questionnaire data that allows to determine the multifaceted aspects of graduates in determining their professional skills, preparation for scientific research activities, personal, social-ethical attitudes and other such aspects; mental testing method; method of conducting practical work games; proficiency testing method; method of checking reviews; interview method; certification method; extensive use of special methods such as the rating method.

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